

INFLUENCE OF THE THERMO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES ON THE PREDICTIONS OF THE CURE-INDUCED DEFORMATIONS IN THERMOSET-BASED COMPOSITE PARTS

Antoine Parmentier, Benoît Wucher and David Dumas

Composite Structures and Processes, Cenaero ASBL
Bâtiment Eole, Rue des Frères Wright 29, B-6041 Gosselies, Belgium
Email: antoine.parmentier@cenaero.be, web page: <http://www.cenaero.be>

Keywords: Composite, Simulation, Cure, Distortion, Spring-in

ABSTRACT

During the cure of thermoset resins from liquid state to solid state, the cured component may experience undesired deformations due to thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage. Environmental conditions such as contact with the mould and pressure exerted on the part prevent these deformations from developing freely and result in a build-up of internal stresses. Upon demoulding, some of these internal stresses are released, resulting in the presence of distortions. Being able to accurately predict the cure-induced deformations is therefore a crucial design step in order to avoid costly trial-and-error or empirical approaches currently used in mould design. The present study aims at determining the numerical model complexity level in terms of material properties and boundary conditions allowing to predict the cure-induced spring-in with sufficient accuracy. The results of the study show the influence of the material characterisation and representative boundary conditions on the ability to obtain reliable results and accurate predictions. Through a sensitivity analysis, four material properties have been determined to have a large influence on the accuracy of the numerical predictions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The polymerisation reaction, or curing, which transforms the liquid thermoset resin to solid, induces internal stresses within the part being produced. During this change of state, the part deforms due to thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage of the resin. The contact conditions with the mould as well as the pressure exerted on the part prevent these deformations from developing freely resulting in a build-up of internal stresses. Upon demoulding, some of these internal stresses are released, resulting in the appearance of distortions. Being able to predict the cure-induced deformations is therefore a key point in order to avoid the costly trial-and-error or empirical approaches currently used in mould design. One of the main challenges behind an accurate prediction of the residual stresses and deformations is the use of a model complexity level suited to the problem studied.

The present study aims at determining the required level of complexity for the numerical model in terms of thermo-mechanical properties and boundary conditions to predict the cure-induced deformations with sufficient accuracy. To quantify these cure-induced deformations, the spring-in angle $\Delta\theta$ is measured between the nominal geometry or mould geometry and the cured geometry. Figure 1 illustrates the methodology used to compute the spring-in angle.

Figure 1: Definition of the spring-in angle.

2 METHOD

2.1 Numerical

The numerical prediction methodology used consists of performing coupled chemical-thermal-mechanical Finite Elements (FE) calculations using ABAQUS with the help of user material subroutines. It was assumed that the temperature gradient across the thickness of the part was negligible due to the low thickness of the part. As a result of which, a transient thermal analysis was not performed and the temperature was considered to be uniform throughout the part. However the cure cycle temperatures were included in the transient chemical-mechanical analysis to evaluate the material models. The details of the model follow the approach suggested by Svanberg and Holmberg [1] who consider a simplified linear viscoelastic behaviour of the material where time-temperature-degree of cure superposition is applied. Three of the main assumptions made are: (i) the stresses and strains are assumed to be zero until gelation, (ii) the thermal expansion is assumed to be linear within each material state, and (iii) the material properties are kept constant for each relevant state, rubbery or glassy, of the resin. The material used is the Hexcel AS4/8552 prepreg plain-weave fabric. The present study evaluates the latter assumption through two sets of material properties:

- the first is taken from literature [2-4] and considers constant material properties for each relevant state, rubbery or glassy, of the resin. The missing properties of the carbon fabric prepreg have been determined using the Classical Laminate Theory from the properties of the UD prepreg 8552/AS4 and micromechanics calculations. The set of properties used is presented in Table 1;
- the second is based on characterisation tests on the material to determine the evolution of the properties along the cure cycle. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) and tensile tests were performed in order to obtain the Young's and shear moduli as a function of temperature. Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA) was also performed to characterise the thermal and chemical dilatation or shrinkage coefficients. These coefficients have been considered to be constant for each material state.

The transition from the rubbery to glassy state occurs when the resin temperature reaches its glass transition temperature T_g which is assumed to depend only on the degree of cure X . The model used to predict the glass transition temperature T_g as a function of the degree of cure X and the kinetic model are those used in [2] for the 8552 resin.

Properties		Rubbery	Glassy
$E_1=E_2$	[MPa]	66190	68000
E_3	[MPa]	165	10000
ν_{21}	–	0.001	0.220
ν_{31}	–	0.002	0.072
ν_{23}	–	0.833	0.490
G_{12}	[MPa]	44.3	5000
$G_{13}=G_{23}$	[MPa]	42.9	4500
$\alpha_1=\alpha_2$	[1/°C]	-7.11E-07	2.5E-06
α_3	[1/°C]	0.0002	62.5E-06
$\beta_1=\beta_2$	–	9.3E-04* $\beta(X)$	5.3E-02* $\beta(X)$
β_3	–	$\beta(X)$	$\beta(X)$

Table 1: Properties, taken from the literature, used in the simulations. Subscripts 1 and 2 indicate the fibres directions of the fabric prepreg. α and β stand for the coefficients of thermal expansion and the chemical shrinkage, respectively. The chemical shrinkage is provided as a function of the degree of cure X in [2].

Three boundary conditions with increasing complexity were also compared to determine the most efficient combination of material properties and boundary conditions:

- Freestanding cure (NC) which means that the part is free to deform during cure. The rigid body motions are blocked to prevent numerical convergence issues;
- Fully-constrained cure (FC): all the nodes are blocked during cure. A demoulding step is performed after curing to release the nodes and predict the deformation due to stress relaxation;
- Autoclave conditions (Autoclave): applying a pressure on the top of the part to account for the effect of the vacuum bag and modeling the tool as a rigid body. Modeling the mould as a rigid part is close to reality since the tool used in autoclave is made of Invar which exhibits a low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). These boundary conditions are intended to be close to those encountered experimentally in the autoclave: the autoclave pressure keeps the part against the mould and the mould prevents the angle to close during cure.

2.2 Experimental

An experimental study was performed on Z-shaped angle bracket parts manufactured on Invar tooling in order to validate the numerical model. These parts were fabricated using Hexcel AS4/8552 prepreg plain-weave fabrics and cured in an autoclave. Invar tooling was chosen due to its low CTE. This lowers the mismatch between the coefficients of thermal expansion and limits the influence of the thermal dilatation of the mould and the tool-part interaction in the simulation. Using a mould with a higher CTE, the tool-part interaction can have a significant effect on the deformations, as previously shown by other researchers [5]. The Z-shaped parts are 150mm long with 100mm long flanges. Three cases, with different stacking sequences, have been manufactured and simulated in order to evaluate the robustness of the numerical model:

- 15 plies of carbon fabric prepreg, symmetric: $[\pm 45^\circ/0-90^\circ]_{4s}$
- 10 plies of carbon fabric prepreg, symmetric: $[(\pm 45/0-90)_2/\pm 45]_s$
- 8 plies of carbon fabric prepreg, asymmetric: $[\pm 45^\circ/0-90^\circ/(\pm 45^\circ/0-90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)]_s$

The cure cycle applied is a cycle used by aeronautic companies while curing secondary structures.

The indicator of the deformation is the spring-in angle. The distortions of the parts are measured

using a Nikon MMDx100 laser scanner mounted on a 7-axis Metrology-grade MCA II arm. The declared accuracy is $54\ \mu\text{m}$ which leads to an uncertainty of 0.1° on the spring-in angle measured. The two angles of the Z-shape have been measured and abbreviations A1 and A2 in the following represent the male and the female angle of the tool, respectively. The angles were measured along the part length and the presented spring-in is the average of 10 measurements per part and per angle. The standard deviation of these ten measurements has been added to the measurement uncertainty of 0.1° to establish the experimental error bars on the figures in the following section.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental measurements are compared to the numerical predictions in Figure 2. The two angles were measured and are referenced A1 and A2 as explained in the previous section. In numerical predictions, as the stacking sequence is symmetric, no significant differences were measured between the two angles and only one angle has been reported in the following. The results showed that two numerical cases give predictions within the uncertainty of the experimental: 'NC-Literature' and 'Autoclave-Tests'. These two cases are respectively the ones requiring the minimum and maximum effort and computational cost: computations ran in 10 minutes and 35 minutes, respectively, on 6 processors.

For both sets of properties, the 'Autoclave' boundary conditions results fall between the other two, as expected: the 'Autoclave' case is more constrained than the 'Freestanding cure', where the part is free to deform, and less constrained than the 'Fully-constrained cure'. Another expected observation is that the refinement of the boundary conditions, within a set of properties, leads to an improvement of the numerical predictions with respect to the experimental measurements. This can only be observed using the set of material properties resulting from the characterisation tests. This observation gives trust in the results obtained using these properties compared to the literature set.

The same observations can be made on the other two cases (see Figures 3 and 4) and confirm the model's validity, even on a slightly asymmetrical lay-up. Only one experimental measurement (angle A1) is presented on the asymmetric case (see Figure 4) as an abnormal resin rich region was present at the angle A2 affecting the measured value. The predictions of the 'NC-Literature' set are, for the three cases studied, close to the experimental. Therefore, it seems as though, for the material system used and common stacking sequences, good results can already be achieved at a minimum computational cost. However, representative boundary conditions and accurate material properties allow to ensure the reliability of the predictions.

Figure 2: Reliability of numerical predictions of spring-in angle on a symmetric stacking sequence of 15 plies of carbon fabric prepreg. "NC", "FC" and "Autoclave" are the different boundary conditions while "Literature" and "Tests" refer to the set of properties used.

Figure 3: Reliability of numerical predictions of spring-in angle on a symmetric stacking sequence of 10 plies of carbon fabric prepreg . “NC”, “FC” and “Autoclave” are the different boundary conditions while “Literature” and “Tests” refer to the set of properties used.

Figure 4: Reliability of numerical predictions of spring-in angle on a asymmetric stacking sequence of 8 plies of carbon fabric prepreg . “NC”, “FC” and “Autoclave” are the different boundary conditions while “Literature” and “Tests” refer to the set of properties used.

The comparison between numerical predictions and experimental measurements on the three different cases have shown the importance of the material characterisation and representative boundary conditions to get reliable results and accurate predictions. This high dependence on material characterisation accuracy raises the interest in understanding the dependency of the prediction accuracy on the individual material properties of the model. This understanding can be used to define priorities with respect to which tests should be performed and which values can be taken from literature to reduce design costs. To establish this dependency, a sensitivity analysis on the material properties was performed (see Figure 5). The sensitivity analysis has been performed using all the characterised properties but one, taken from the literature set. Each case is denoted by this literature property. For example, the case 'E3' uses the characterised material data set, except for the out-of-plane Young's modulus E3. In the 'v' case, the Poisson's coefficients have all been taken simultaneously equal to their values found in the literature. The values presented in Figure 5 are the variations of the spring-in angle with respect to the reference case, using all the properties from the characterisation tests. The variation, expressed in percentages, are computed as follows:

$$Variation = \left(\frac{\Delta\theta - \Delta\theta_{REF}}{\Delta\theta_{REF}} \right) * 100 \quad (1)$$

Four properties that involve the entire material characterisation tests have been identified to have significant influence on the numerical predictions:

- Transverse Young's modulus, E_3 ;
- Shear modulus G_{13} ;
- Coefficient of thermal expansion in the transverse direction α_3 ;
- Coefficient of chemical shrinkage in the transverse direction β_3 .

The two cases ' $\alpha_1=\alpha_2=0$ ' and ' $\beta_1=\beta_2=0$ ' consider the influence of setting these coefficients to zero instead of the values listed in Table 1, which is an assumption commonly used in the literature due to the low values of these coefficients. The results show the relevance of this assumption.

Figure 5: Sensitivity analysis of the material properties on the numerical predictions

4 CONCLUSION

The comparison between numerical predictions and experimental measurements has shown the importance of representative boundary conditions and material characterisation in order to obtain reliable results and accurate predictions. The sensitivity analysis performed has highlighted the most influential material properties which should be characterised : transverse Young's modulus, shear modulus G_{13} , coefficients of thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage in the transverse direction. This appears to be the minimum characterisation required to obtain reliable results and involves the entire characterisation tests performed. Future work would be to evaluate whether the evolution of the moduli in rubbery state needs to be characterised or whether their evolution during the transition should be carefully recorded. This could remove the need for DMA tests and significantly reduce the effort required for material characterisation tests.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.M. Svanberg and J.A. Holmberg, Predictions of shape distortions Part I. FE-implementation of a path dependent constitutive model, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 35(6), 2004, pp. 711-772 ([doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2004.02.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2004.02.005)).
- [2] N. Ersoy and al., Development of spring-in angle during cure of a thermosetting composite, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 36(12), 2005, pp. 1700-1706 ([doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2005.02.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2005.02.013)).

- [3] N. Ersoy and al., Development of the properties of a carbon fibre reinforced thermosetting composite through cure, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 41(3), 2010, pp. 401-409 ([doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2009.11.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2009.11.007)).
- [4] J.A. Artero and al., On the influence of filling level in CFRP aircraft fuel tank subjected to high velocity impacts, *Composite Structures*, 107, 2014, pp. 570-577 ([doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.08.036](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.08.036)).
- [5] G. Fernlund, G. Twigg and A. Poursartip, Tool-part interaction in composite processing Part 1: experimental investigation and analytical model, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 35(1), 2004, pp. 121-133 ([doi:10.1016/S1359-835X\(03\)00131-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(03)00131-3)).